

1 **Modeling heat and mass transfer with water condensation process inside fruits bulk**

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5

6 **Abstract**

7 After harvesting, blueberries are precooled and stored in crates or cylindrical containers in cold
8 rooms before distribution. Temperature fluctuations, cold chain breaks, or exposure to warm air
9 during loading/unloading can cause water condensation on the product surface. These events
10 lead to defects in appearance, promote the formation of spores and the growth of
11 microorganisms, and accelerate deterioration. In this study, we present a model of heat and mass
12 transfer in the bulk fruit, including condensation, for two different configurations: a container
13 with insulation at the top and bottom, and a container without insulation. The model predicts
14 the air and product temperatures, as well as water condensation within the container. We
15 validated the model against experimental data, showing relatively good agreement between the
16 simulated and experimental values (RMSE < 0.8°C). Additionally, the model was used to
17 demonstrate that water condensation occurred predominantly in the top area of the container.

18 Keywords: Chilled fruits, Cold chain breaks, Natural convection, Water condensation.

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23 **Nomenclature**

- 24 A Surface area, m^2
- 25 A_{spec} Specific surface of the blueberries, m^2 of product surface per m^3 of porous medium
- 26 a_w Water activity
- 27 Bi Biot number
- 28 C Water vapor concentration in air, $kg.m^{-3}$
- 29 C_1 Water content in the air of porous medium, $kg.m^{-3}$ of air
- 30 C_2 Water content in the condensate of porous medium, $kg.m^{-3}$ of porous medium
- 31 C_3 Reduction of water content in the product of porous medium, $kg.m^{-3}$ of porous medium
- 32 C_p Specific heat at constant pressure, $J.kg^{-1}.K^{-1}$
- 33 D Internal diameter of container, m
- 34 D_{eff} Effective mass diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium, $m^2.s^{-1}$
- 35 D_v Diffusivity of water vapor in air, $m^2.s^{-1}$
- 36 d Average diameter of blueberries, m
- 37 g Gravitation acceleration, $m.s^{-2}$
- 38 H_{evap} Latent heat of evaporation, $J.kg^{-1}$
- 39 h Convective heat transfer coefficient, $W.m^{-2}.K^{-1}$
- 40 h_m Convective mass transfer coefficient, $m.s^{-1}$
- 41 K Permeability, m^2

42	k	Thermal conductivity, $\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$
43	k_s	Skin mass transfer coefficient, $\text{kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}.\text{Pa}^{-1}$
44	L	Height of the container, m
45	L_c	Characteristic length, m
46	Le	Lewis number
47	M	Molecular mass, kg.mol^{-1}
48	m	Mass, kg
49	Nu	Nusselt number
50	Pr	Prandtl number
51	P	Pressure, Pa
52	R	Universal gas constant, $\text{J.mol}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$
53	R_{skin}	Skin mass transfer resistance, s.m^{-1}
54	RH	Relative humidity, %
55	r	Radial position, m
56	Sc	Schmidt number
57	T	Temperature, K
58	t	Time, s
59	V	Volume, m^3
60	v	Fluid superficial velocity, m.s^{-1}
61	X	Mass fraction

62	ρ	Density, kg.m ⁻³
63	β	Thermal expansion coefficient of air, K ⁻¹
64	ε	Porosity
65	μ	Dynamic viscosity, Pa.s
66	ν	Kinematic viscosity, m ² .s ⁻¹
67	τ	Tortuosity
68		Indices
69	a	Air
70	d	dew
71	eq.	Equivalent
72	exp.	Experiment
73	p	Products
74	ref.	Reference
75	s	surface
76	sat	Saturated
77	sim	Simulation
78	v	water vapor
79	w	Wall
80	∞	Surrounding air
81		

82 **1. Introduction**

83 Due to their high nutritional value, blueberries are among the most important soft fruits
84 and are often called a "superfood" for this reason. However, blueberries are highly perishable
85 products (Chiabrando and Giacalone, 2011) and their shelf life is about six days at room
86 temperature (Eum et al., 2013). The optimal storage conditions for blueberries are a temperature
87 of around 0°C, and a relative humidity of 90-95%. Such conditions can extend their shelf life
88 up to 18 days (Concha-Meyer et al., 2015). Due to complex cold chain logistics, horticultural
89 products are not always maintained under their optimal conditions at the different stages in the
90 cold chain (Chaomuang et al., 2022; Loisel et al., 2021; Ndraha et al., 2018).

91 Regarding the blueberry supply chain, Steynberg et al. (2022) studied the upstream
92 stages in South Africa. The authors observed a large number of temperature and chilling injury
93 spikes and breaks during transport following harvest, in the packing house and during the forced
94 cooling stages. Storage or transport of blueberries at inappropriate temperatures leads to greater
95 moisture loss, decay incidence, and softening (Paniagua et al., 2014). Overall, poor temperature
96 management can cause fruit and vegetable waste ranging from 25 to 50% (Chaomuang et al.,
97 2022).

98 Water condensation can occur on horticultural products due to small temperature
99 fluctuations under high humidity, or it may occur due to high temperature differences when cold
100 products are subjected to ambient temperature and medium humidity. In both these cases,
101 condensation occurs when the product's surface temperature is below the air dew point. When
102 the product's surface temperature increases to a temperature above the air dew temperature, the
103 condensed water on the surface may evaporate back into the surrounding air (Lequentrec et al.,
104 2023; Linke et al., 2021). Water condensation remaining on the product surface is undesirable
105 because it leads to defects in the product's appearance and can promote microbial growth (Linke
106 and Geyer, 2013). On the other hand, condensed water can also have positive effects on the

107 product. It reduces transpiration, as well as product weight loss and shrinkage (Linke et al.,
108 2021). Condensation on the product surface is characterized by complex, temporal and spatial
109 variations in heat and mass transfer processes because of the complexity of the airflow. This
110 complexity is due to the shape of the products, the nature of the packaging, and the types of
111 pallet arrangement (Lequentrec et al., 2023).

112 Numerous experimental and numerical studies have examined weight loss related to
113 temperature and humidity during transportation and storage (Chaomuang et al., 2024;
114 Chourasia and Goswami, 2007; Duret et al., 2014; Laguerre et al., 2023). However, few studies
115 consider water condensation in the cold supply chain. Gottschalk et al. (2007) developed a
116 mathematical model to determine the condensed water on a single fruit surface during
117 rewarming. The amount of simulated water condensation closely matched measured water
118 condensation, although the rate of condensation and evaporation was faster in the simulation
119 than in the experiment. Linke et al. (2021) developed the wetness detectors to measure
120 condensed water on the surface of fruit. The experimental result showed that during apple
121 rewarming, the convective mass transfer coefficient was $6.52 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m.s}^{-1}$ during the
122 condensation phase, and $3.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m.s}^{-1}$ during the evaporation phase. In a related study,
123 Lequentrec et al. (2023) studied water condensation on the surface of an orange during a break
124 in the cold chain. The results showed that the simulation slightly overpredicted the condensed
125 water on the product surface. Linke et al. (2023) used a wetness sensor to detect condensation
126 on an apple surface during controlled atmosphere storage. The duration of dewpoint undershoot
127 was different from the time of active condensation measured by the wetness sensor. These
128 studies determined amounts of condensed water as well as the total retention time of condensate
129 on the product surface. However, these studies focused on a single product, representing a
130 limitation in more complex geometry.

131 In this study, we aimed to develop a CFD model of heat and mass transfer in packaging
132 filled with blueberries subjected to cold chain breaks. We used a porous medium approach that
133 includes natural convection. The model evaluated two types of containers: one with insulation
134 on the top and bottom, and one without insulation. The model was implemented using the
135 COMSOL software, with parameters from the literature, calculated or identified experimentally.
136 The model's predictions for the air and product temperatures were then compared with the
137 experimental values for validation.

138 **2. Numerical modeling**

139 We adapted a two-dimensional (2D) axisymmetric transient model, previously
140 developed by Urquiola et al. (2017) for frozen carrots, to simulate airflow, heat and mass
141 transfer, and water condensation in bulk-stored blueberries exposed to cold chain breaks. As a
142 first approach to study these complex phenomena, two simplified configurations were studied,
143 one with insulation at the top and bottom, and one without insulation (Fig. 1). The packaging
144 was also simplified (non-permeable material and no macro-perforation) to avoid vapor
145 exchange with ambient air. The 2D calculation domain is shown in Fig. 1c.

146 The following main assumptions were made for simplification purposes.

- 147 1. The stack of blueberries was considered to be a porous medium.
- 148 2. A 2D axisymmetric model was implemented.
- 149 3. Laminar airflow was considered in the container.
- 150 4. The Boussinesq approximation was used: the air density is assumed constant (ρ_a is the
151 value at $T_{ref}=4^\circ\text{C}$) except in the gravity term to take into account natural convection
152 where $\rho = \rho_a[1 - \beta(T_a - T_{ref})]$ (Laguerre et al., 2008).
- 153 5. The internal thermal resistance of blueberries was neglected. The Biot number of a
154 blueberry was calculated using $Bi = \frac{hL_c}{k_p}$ is around $0.024 < 0.1$, calculated using thermal

155 conductivity of blueberry $0.57 \text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$ (section 2.4.5); the convective heat transfer
156 coefficient is $5.5 \text{ W.m}^{-2}.\text{K}^{-1}$ and L_c is the characteristic length calculated as the ratio of
157 the blueberry volume to blueberry surface area. From a study of Allais and Alvarez
158 (2001), convective heat transfer under condensation on the surface can increase up to
159 two times in the worst case. By including the effect of latent heat of
160 condensation/evaporation on the fruit surface (and neglecting radiation) in the Biot
161 number through the heat transfer coefficient, the Biot number is $Bi = \frac{2hL_c}{k_p} = 0.048$. Even
162 in this case, the Biot number remains smaller than 0.1.

- 163 6. Internal water transfer resistance inside the blueberries was neglected.
- 164 7. The temperature of the external side of the container wall was known as a function of
165 time from measurements.
- 166 8. The radiative heat transfer between the container wall and the blueberries and between
167 the blueberries was neglected.
- 168 9. The dispersion term in the energy equation for the porous medium was neglected.
- 169 10. Plastic packaging is permeable materials to gases and water vapor. Permeability is a
170 temperature dependent property of packaging (Keller and Kouzes, 2017; Matar et al.,
171 2018). To simplify the model, there is no mass exchange between the external air and
172 the internal air.

173 2.1 Governing equations

174 The following equations, which consider momentum, energy, and mass transfer, were
175 solved based on the previously stated assumptions.

176 2.1.1 Continuity and momentum equations with the Boussinesq approximation.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{\rho_a}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \frac{\rho_a}{\varepsilon^2} (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\vec{\nabla} P + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{v} - \frac{\mu}{K} \vec{v} - \rho_a \beta (T_a - T_{ref}) \vec{g} \quad (2)$$

177 Where ε is the porosity of the stack of blueberries, \vec{v} is the superficial velocity of the fluid in
 178 the porous medium (m.s⁻¹) or Darcy velocity, μ is the dynamic viscosity of air (Pa.s), K is the
 179 permeability of the porous medium (i.e its ability to transmit fluids, m²) (section 2.4.6), and β is
 180 the thermal coefficient of volumetric expansion (K⁻¹).

181 2.1.2 Energy conservation equation

182 The energy conservation equations for air, Eq. (3) and also for the product, Eq. (4) are
 183 coupled through the convective heat transfer. Additionally, the latent heat of water evaporation
 184 is accounted for in the energy conservation equation of the product. The heat of respiration of
 185 the product is neglected in the energy equation due to its low contribution (0.039 W.kg⁻¹ at 5°C
 186 and 0.202 W.kg⁻¹ at 20°C) (ASHRAE, 2022).

$$\rho_a C p_a \varepsilon \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\vec{v} \rho_a C p_a T_a) = k_a \nabla^2 T_a + h A_{spec} (T_p - T_a) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_p C p_p (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = k_{eq} \nabla^2 T_p + h A_{spec} (T_a - T_p) + \left(\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial t} \right) H_{evap} \quad (4)$$

187 Where k_{eq} is the equivalent thermal conductivity of the porous medium (W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹), A_{spec} is
 188 the specific blueberries' surface area defined as the blueberries' surface area within the total
 189 volume of a container (m⁻¹), h is the heat transfer coefficient between the internal air and the
 190 blueberries, H_{evap} is the latent heat of evaporation, C_2 and C_3 are described in Section 2.1.3.

191 2.1.3 Water mass balance equation

192 The total water mass balance equation is described in Eq. (5) in a similar manner as that
 193 described in Urquiola et al. (2017).

$$\frac{\partial (\varepsilon C_1 + C_2 + C_3)}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla C_1 = D_{eff} \nabla^2 C_1 \quad (5)$$

194 where C_1 is the water content in the air of porous medium (kg per m³ of air), C_2 is the water
 195 content in the condensate of porous medium (kg per m³ of porous medium) refers to the amount
 196 of water that has condensed and accumulated on the surface of the blueberries within the porous
 197 medium, C_3 represents the water content loss ($C_3 < 0$) in the product at a given time (kg per m³
 198 of porous medium) refers to the internal water lost from the blueberries due to transpiration,
 199 and D_{eff} is the effective mass diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium. A schematic of
 200 the mass balance for the air, condensed water and product is shown in Fig. 2.

201 The relative humidity (RH , %) relates the water content in the air to the saturated vapor
 202 concentration (Shrivastava et al., 2023).

$$RH = \frac{C_1}{C_{sat}(T_p)} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

203 The water condensation equation is shown in Eq. (7). Water condensation occurs when
 204 the water vapor concentration in the air is higher than the saturated water vapor concentration
 205 at the product temperature ($C_1 > C_{sat}(T_p)$). Water evaporation occurs when the water vapor
 206 concentration in the air is lower than the saturated water vapor concentration at the product
 207 temperature ($C_1 < C_{sat}(T_p)$) and if condensate is already present on the surface of the product
 208 ($C_2 > 0$).

$$\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} h_m A_{spec} (C_1 - C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 > C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ (Condensation)} \\ h_m A_{spec} (C_1 - C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 < C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ and } C_2 > 0 \text{ (Evaporation)} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

209 Where h_m is mass transfer coefficient (m.s⁻¹).

210 The saturated vapor concentration, $C_{sat}(T)$ is calculated from Eq. (8), assuming that air
 211 is an ideal gas.

$$C_{sat}(T) = \frac{P_{sat}(T)M}{RT} \quad (8)$$

212 where $P_{sat}(T)$ is the saturated vapor pressure (Pa).

213 Eq. (9) describes the product dehydration, which occurs when the water vapor
214 concentration in the air is lower than the water vapor concentration in the air in equilibrium
215 with the product ($C_1 < a_w C_{sat}(T_p)$) and if there is no water at the product surface ($C_2 = 0$).

$$\frac{\partial C_3}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_m} + R_{skin}} \times A_{spec} (C_1 - a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 < a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ and } C_2 = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } (C_1 > a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ or } C_2 > 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

216 where R_{skin} is the skin resistance of the product (s.m^{-1}) and a_w is the water activity of blueberry,
217 assumed to be one.

218 The Lewis analogy was applied to calculate the mass transfer coefficient as shown in
219 Eq. (10).

$$h_m = \frac{h}{\rho_a C p_a} \quad (10)$$

220 2.2 Initial conditions

221 The initial velocity of the air was assumed to be zero.

$$\vec{v}_{(t=0)} = 0 \quad (11)$$

222 The initial air temperature and product temperatures were obtained from measurements.

$$T_{a,(t=0)} = T_{p,(t=0)} = T_0 \quad (12)$$

223 The water content in air (C_1) and in condensate (C_2) were assumed to be zero initially.

224 The water content loss in the product (C_3) was zero initially.

$$C_{1,(t=0)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$C_{2,(t=0)} = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$C_{3,(t=0)} = 0 \quad (15)$$

2.3 Boundary conditions

The velocity at the walls was zero due to the no-slip condition. There was no mass transfer across the walls, and no heat flux occurred through the insulated walls (top and bottom walls in Configuration 1). The heat flux on the insulated wall was assumed to be zero.

$$\left. \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial z} \right]_{z=\pm L/2} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial z} \right]_{z=\pm L/2} = 0 \quad (17)$$

On the non-insulated walls, the heat flux by conduction through the wall was assumed to be transferred by conduction to air or product as a proportion of their volume fraction according to Equations (18) and (19).

$$\varepsilon \frac{k_w}{l_w} (T_w - T_a) = k_a \nabla T_a \cdot \vec{n} \quad (18)$$

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \frac{k_w}{l_w} (T_w - T_p) = k_{eq} \nabla T_p \cdot \vec{n} \quad (19)$$

where $k_w = 0.17 \text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$ is the thermal conductivity of the wall (polypropylene) (Urquiola et al., 2017) and $l_w = 1 \text{ mm}$, its thickness. T_w represents the wall temperature and was defined as a function of time based on measurement.

Finally, packaging walls were assumed to be non-permeable materials to water vapor.

$$\nabla C_1 \cdot \vec{n} = 0 \quad (20)$$

2.4 Parameter identification

To solve the differential equations, parameters were determined through measurements, calculations or the literature. Additionally, for some of the parameters detailed in this section,

239 the uncertainty of these parameters was also characterized in order to evaluate their further
240 impact on the final results obtained using the model (Section 5.3).

241 2.4.1 Product bulk porosity

242 The porosity of a porous medium is defined as a fraction of the volume of voids (volume
243 of air) over the total volume. The porosity is evaluated by measuring the void volume of the
244 porous medium using water. The porosity (ϵ) was 0.40.

245 2.4.2 Diameter and density of blueberries

246 The mass of 100 blueberries was determined using a scale (OHAUS EX10202) with a
247 precision of ± 0.01 g. The volume was measured by the water displacement method and the
248 density was calculated to be $1023 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Using the total volume of the 100 blueberries, the
249 average equivalent diameter of a blueberry was estimated using Eq. (21), resulting in a value
250 of 0.0148 m.

$$d = \left(\frac{6V_p}{100\pi}\right)^{1/3} \quad (21)$$

251 2.4.3 Specific surface

252 The specific surface is defined as the ratio between the total surface of a product and the
253 total volume of container and was calculated using Eq. (22).

$$A_{spec} = \frac{A_{total\ surface}}{V_{container}} = \frac{6(1-\epsilon)}{d} \quad (22)$$

254 The calculated specific surface (A_{spec}) was 243 m^{-1} .

255 2.4.4 Product specific heat capacity

256 The specific heat capacity (Cp_p) of the blueberry was obtained from ASHRAE (2022)
257 and the value was $3830 \text{ J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at 4°C

258 2.4.5 Thermal conductivity of product

259 The thermal conductivity of the blueberry (k_p) was obtained from Mercali et al. (2011).

260 The thermal conductivity of the blueberry is $0.57 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$.

261 2.4.6 Permeability

262 The bulk product permeability was calculated by using the Carman–Kozeny equation

263 (Nield and Bejan, 2013).

$$K = \frac{d^2 \varepsilon^3}{180(1 - \varepsilon)^2} \quad (23)$$

264 where d is the average diameter of a blueberry. The calculated permeability is $2.16 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2$.

265 2.4.7 Skin resistance

266 The skin resistance, R_{skin} describes the resistance of water passing through the skin of

267 a blueberry and can be calculated by Eq. (24) as reported by Becker et al. (1996).

$$R_{skin} = \frac{M}{R \cdot T_{ref} \cdot k_s} \quad (24)$$

268 where R represents the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), T_{ref} is the reference

269 temperature (277.15 K), and M is the molar mass of water ($18.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). The skin

270 mass transfer coefficient, k_s is $2.19 \times 10^{-9} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}$.

271 2.4.8 Equivalent thermal conductivity

272 The equivalent thermal conductivity of the bulk product was determined using an

273 experimental method and by solving a one-dimensional heat conduction model. A value k_{eq}

274 of $0.18 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ was applied in the model. Details of experiment and determination of

275 equivalent thermal conductivity are presented in the Supplementary Materials (Section A.1)

276

277 2.4.9 Convective heat transfer coefficient

278 The Churchill correlation for natural convection for spheres was used to calculate the
279 Nusselt number (Holman, 2010).

$$Nu = 2 + \frac{0.589Ra^{0.25}}{[1 + (\frac{0.469}{Pr})^{0.563}]^{0.444}} \quad (25)$$

280 where Ra is the Rayleigh number calculated using Eq. (26).

$$Ra = GrPr = \frac{g\beta(T_p - T_\infty)d^3}{\nu^2} Pr \quad (26)$$

281 where Gr is the Grashof number, Pr is the Prandtl number and T_∞ is the surrounding air
282 temperature ($^{\circ}C$).

283 The heat transfer coefficient, h ($W.m^{-2}.K^{-1}$) is calculated from the Nusselt number:

$$Nu = \frac{h \cdot d}{k_a} \quad (27)$$

284 where d is diameter of a blueberry (m) and k_a is thermal conductivity of air.

285 In this study, the temperature difference between the product and the air was observed
286 to be between 0 and $2.2^{\circ}C$. The Rayleigh number ranged between 0 and 971 and the Nusselt
287 number varied between 2.0 and 4.5. As a result, the convective heat transfer coefficient varies
288 between 3.4 and $7.6 W.m^{-2}.K^{-1}$ with an average value of $5.5 W.m^{-2}.K^{-1}$.

289 2.4.10 Effective mass diffusivity

290 The effective diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium depend on the mass
291 diffusivity of water vapor in air and the porosity as given by Eq. (28) obtained from Nield and
292 Bejan (2013):

$$D_{eff} = D_v \varepsilon \quad (28)$$

293 where ε is the porosity of the porous medium and D_v is the diffusivity of the water vapor in the
294 air at a reference temperature ($2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) obtained from Cengel and Ghajar (2020). The
295 nominal value obtained is $D_{eff} = 8.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

296 Some studies include porous medium tortuosity into effective mass diffusivity (Nield &
297 Bejan, 2013). To evaluate its impact in the parameter sensitivity analysis, the minimum value
298 of effective mass diffusivity was calculated using Eq. (29):

$$D_{eff} = \frac{D_v \varepsilon}{\tau} \quad (29)$$

299 where τ is the tortuosity calculated from $\tau = \pi/2$ (Lanfrey et al., 2010). The minimum value
300 of the effective mass diffusivity is $5.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

301 For the maximum value of the effective mass diffusivity, the tortuosity, and porosity
302 were not considered. Thus, the effective mass diffusivity was $2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

303 2.5 Numerical Resolution

304 COMSOL Multiphysics (Version 6.3) was used to solve the set of differential equations.
305 The simulations were run on a Windows 10 Pro system with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E3-1240
306 v5 @ 3.50GHz, 64.0 GB of RAM, and a Nvidia Quadro K420 graphics card. Free time stepping
307 was used and the initial time step was set at 0.001 minutes. An automatic physics-controlled
308 mesh (triangular and quadrilateral elements) was created for the numerical study.

309 A mesh sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of the mesh grid on the
310 results obtained. Three different meshes, "Normal", "Fine", and "Finer", were tested for the
311 mesh independence study. For these tests, the simulation of the container with insulation at the
312 top and bottom with an imposed temperature profile was used.

313 Table 1 shows the number of elements and computational time for each mesh. Table 2
314 shows the difference in the air temperature and product temperature results in areas A (bottom

315 center) and B (bottom external) and water condensation at 60 minutes (at the end of heating)
316 between the different meshes.

317 The results in Table 2 show that the variations decrease as the mesh elements increase.
318 The air and product temperature variations between the Fine and Finer meshes are very small
319 and the difference in water condensation was 0.0015 g, accounting for 0.7% of the total water
320 condensation. However, the computational time doubled when using the Finer mesh. Thus, the
321 Fine mesh was chosen for our study.

322 **3. Materials and methods for model validation**

323 3.1 Product

324 This study was carried out using fresh commercial-grade blueberries purchased in a
325 retail store. They were measured to obtain the average diameter according to methodology in
326 section 2.4.2. They were equipped with T type thermocouples at the center.

327 3.2 Containers

328 The blueberries were stored in almost cylindrical plastic (polypropylene) containers
329 with a volume of 1.24 liters (internal diameter 100 mm at the bottom; 120 mm at the top; height
330 130 mm; wall thickness 1.0 mm). Blueberries of different sizes were mixed and placed
331 randomly in the container. For case 1, the containers were insulated at the top and the bottom
332 with expanded polystyrene (EPS) with a thickness of 80 mm. The blueberries were distributed
333 into four distinct sections (A (volume 206 cm³), B (volume 310 cm³), C (volume 225 cm³), and
334 D (volume 310 cm³)) within 3D-printed grid baskets (Fig. 3a). These baskets divided the
335 container into central and near-wall areas on two levels, allowing the analysis of temperature
336 and condensation within the container.

337 3.3 Scenario and studied conditions

338 As in the numerical study, two configurations were studied: (1) container with insulation
339 on the top and bottom, and (2) container without insulation.

340 The first case mimics the case where several containers are stacked one on top of the
341 other with almost no heat flux between them. The second case, a container was not insulated
342 on the top or the bottom and was placed on a grid allowing heat transfer with the external air at
343 the top and the bottom. The temperatures of the external side of the walls were measured using
344 a type-T thermocouple and defined as boundary conditions in the model.

345 3.4 Experimental set-up.

346 To simulate cold chain breaks, containers filled with blueberries were initially placed in
347 a refrigerator at 4°C for 24 hours to stabilize the temperature. They were then exposed to 20°C
348 for 60 minutes, followed by refrigerated storage for 23 hours.

349 For containers with insulation at the top and bottom, an additional temperature scenario
350 was performed to measure the air and product temperatures. After temperature stabilization, the
351 cold containers filled with blueberries were heated at 25°C for 120 minutes, followed by
352 refrigerated storage for 22 hours. Two additional temperature scenarios were performed to
353 measure water condensation. After temperature stabilization, the cold containers filled with
354 blueberries were subjected to different scenarios: the first container was placed at 25°C for 60
355 minutes, and the second container was heated at 25°C for 120 minutes.

356 3.5 Temperature measurement.

357 T-type thermocouples (precision $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ after calibration), calibrated at five different
358 temperatures (-5°C, 0°C, 5°C, 15°C, and 35°C), were connected to a data logger (Keysight
359 DAQ970A), linked to a computer. These thermocouples were used to measure the temperatures
360 of the product, air, and container every minute. Four blueberries in the container were equipped
361 with a thermocouple at their center to measure the product temperature at the center of areas A,

362 B, C, and D, respectively. Additionally, four thermocouples were used to measure the air
363 temperature around the product in the center of each area. The external wall temperatures, as
364 well as the ambient temperature, were also measured. The positions of the thermocouples are
365 shown in Fig. 3b. To specify the position of the thermocouple in the container more precisely,
366 the experiments were repeated with one container. A total of three repetitions was carried out to
367 validate temperature for each configuration.

368 3.6 Water condensation measurement

369 To measure water condensation on the fruit surface, a different container from the one
370 used for temperature measurements was utilized to avoid humidity leakage. Water condensation
371 was measured by weighing the condensed water on the product surface in different areas (A, B,
372 C, and D) of the container. More specifically, after the 60 minutes heating phase, the container
373 was opened and the basket was removed without touching the product. Then each basket was
374 weighed separately. Next, the blueberries were carefully removed from the basket. Each
375 blueberry was dried using absorbent paper, as was the basket. The blueberries were then put
376 back in the basket, and the basket was weighed again using the same scale (OHAUS EX10202,
377 ± 0.01 g accuracy). The amount of condensed water corresponded to the difference between the
378 two measurements, expressed in units of $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ of product. Three repetitions were carried out to
379 validate water condensation measurements for each configuration.

380 To compare measured and simulated condensed water values, the simulated condensed
381 water per unit solid volume ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ of product) was calculated as follows: the total mass of
382 simulated condensed water (g) was then divided by the solid volume fraction ($1-\varepsilon$) to express
383 the results in a comparable unit.

384 3.7 Error calculation

385 The performance of the simulation was evaluated by comparing simulated results to
 386 experimental results. Two types of error were calculated: the maximum difference between the
 387 simulated and experimental temperatures (ΔT_{max}) and the root mean square error (RMSE) of
 388 the temperature. These errors can be defined as:

$$\Delta T_{max} = |T_{exp} - T_{sim}|_{max} \quad (30)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (T_{sim} - T_{exp})^2}{N}} \quad (31)$$

389

390 4. Results and discussion

391 4.1 Air and product temperature and water condensation in the container with insulation

392 Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b show the simulated and experimental air and product temperatures,
 393 respectively, for the insulated container (top and bottom) exposed to 20°C for 60 minutes. There
 394 is relatively good agreement between the experimental and simulated values. Both the air and
 395 product temperatures showed the same behavior. The air and product temperatures were almost
 396 equal. This is explained by the low thermal inertia of the air associated with the low air velocity
 397 due to natural convection. In fact, the thermal characteristic time of the air is less than 1 second:

$$398 (\tau_a = \varepsilon \cdot \rho_a \cdot Cp_a / h \cdot A_{spec} = 0.4 \text{ seconds}). \text{ The air and product temperatures mainly depend}$$

399 on the radial position: the further from the wall, the more the temperature variation imposed at
 400 the wall was delayed. At a given radial position, the temperature was slightly higher near the
 401 top, the difference being more pronounced in the experimental results. This temperature
 402 difference between the top and bottom positions can be explained by natural convection
 403 phenomena in the container (thermal stratification).

404 In the first scenario (Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b), during the first 60 minutes, the container
405 (initially at 4°C) was exposed to room temperature. It was heated from the side wall causing
406 both the product and the air temperatures near the wall (B and D) to increase rapidly because
407 of the large difference between the air or product temperatures and the wall temperature. In
408 contrast, the product and air temperatures at the center of the container (A and C) increased, as
409 expected, but more slowly. After 60 minutes, the container was returned to the refrigerator
410 (4°C). As the container was cooled from the side wall, the air and the product temperatures in
411 zones B and D decreased rapidly while those in the central area continued to increase for 60
412 minutes because the thermal radial gradient ($\frac{\partial T_P}{\partial r}$) was still positive near the center. In the second
413 scenario, the container was exposed to 25°C for 120 minutes (Supplementary Materials, Section
414 A.2), showing the behavior of air and product temperature similar to that in the first scenario.

415 Both simulations, with two different scenarios, agree with the experiment results. For
416 example, the model describes well the initial sharp increase in areas B and D (external) as well
417 as the delayed increase in areas A and C (center). It can be seen that the maximum temperature
418 is well predicted in zones D and C (top) also, while it is slightly overestimated in zones A and
419 B (bottom) as the simulation exhibits much lower temperature differences between the top area
420 and the bottom than in the experiments. A similar temperature profile distribution was observed
421 by Urquiola et al. (2017) in frozen fruit exposed to temperature fluctuations.

422 Table 3 presents the errors between the simulated and experimental results for the air
423 and product temperatures. In the first scenario the container was exposed to 20°C for 60 minutes
424 and the maximum temperature difference between the simulated and experimental results was
425 1.6°C in area B for the air, and 2.0°C in area B for the products. In the second scenario, the
426 container was exposed to 25°C for 120 minutes and the maximum temperature difference
427 between the simulated and experimental results was 2.8°C in area D for the air, and 2.2°C in

428 area B for the products. Both scenarios showed the maximum temperature difference, was as
429 expected, in the area close to the wall. It is to be noted that temperature measured and predicted
430 in a zone represents a specific point of the zone and does not represent the average temperature
431 of the zone because the temperature in one zone can be heterogeneous.

432 At 60 minutes (at the end of the heating period), the water condensation on the product
433 surface in the insulated container exposed to 20°C for 60 minutes was measured. The
434 experimental and simulated water condensation in each area in the insulated container are
435 presented in Table 4. The experimental water condensation on the product surface was 0.55
436 g.m⁻³ of product. As shown in Fig. 5a, the experimental results indicate that the highest
437 percentage of water condensation: 33.3% (0.18 g.m⁻³ of product) occurs in area D. The
438 condensed water on the blueberries' surface in the upper zone is shown in Fig. 5b. The water
439 condensation on the container surface was also measured. The condensed water on the container
440 surface was not observed. At 60 minutes, the model predicted the amount of condensed water
441 as 0.28 g.m⁻³ of product (Fig. 5c).

442 To further validate the model's performance, two additional experiments were
443 conducted under different temperature scenarios. The experimental and simulated results are
444 presented in the Supplementary Materials (Section A.3). In the first scenario, the cold container
445 was exposed to 25°C for 60 minutes, resulting in experimental water condensation of 0.62 g·m⁻³
446 on the product surface compared to the model prediction of 0.40 g·m⁻³. The second scenario
447 involved extended exposure to 25°C for 120 minutes, during which experimental condensation
448 increased to 0.94 g·m⁻³, while the model predicted 0.71 g·m⁻³. The ambient temperature and
449 heating duration significantly impact the water condensation on the product surface in the
450 container.

451 In the simulation, the amount of condensed water in the top area was substantially
452 greater (approximately ten times) than that in the bottom area. In contrast, the experiment
453 showed that the amount of condensed water in the top area was approximately three times
454 higher than that in the bottom area. This discrepancy may be explained by water dripping from
455 the upper to lower areas due to the limited surface area available on the product.

456 Overall, the model underpredicted water condensation, although the simulated and
457 experimental results were within the same order of magnitude. The simulated results for area D
458 were close to the experimental data, while the other areas showed substantially lower values
459 compared to the experiment. These differences can be attributed to modeling assumptions,
460 parameter settings, and limitations of the experimental procedure. In particular, opening the
461 container to perform measurements likely induced complex heat and mass transfer between the
462 external air and the package interior. Such disturbances altered the vapor concentration in the
463 closed system and may have affected the amount of condensation observed on the fruit surface
464 while also enhancing convection between the product and the air. Under high convection,
465 airflow occurs across the product surface and large amount of condensed water can accumulate
466 on the product surface (Gottschalk et al., 2007).

467 Accurately measuring the mass of water condensation in the closed container is
468 challenging. Linke et al. (2021) and Lequentrec et al. (2023) used a wetness sensor to measure
469 water condensation on the surface. However, the sensor was capable of measuring the retention
470 time of condensed water but not the mass of the condensed water. In addition, the complex pore
471 structure within the porous medium affects the distribution of air flow and thermal conductivity
472 (Ge et al., 2024).

473 The simulated water condensation in the isolated container with insulation exposed to
474 20°C for 60 minutes in each area is shown in Fig. 5c. Water condensation in every area increased
475 during the first 60 minutes when the container was exposed to the warm temperature. After that,

476 water condensate in areas A and B decreased, while water condensate in areas C and D
477 continually increased when the container was stored in the refrigerator.

478 In order to interpret these results, the numerical results of product temperature
479 distribution, relative humidity, and water condensation were analyzed in Fig. 6–Fig. 8 and the
480 air velocity profile at two different times was analyzed in Fig. 9. Fig. 6–Fig. 8 depict a radial
481 plane of the cylindrical container, with a symmetrical axis on the left side and the wall on the
482 right side. When the container was placed at room temperature, it was heated for 60 minutes,
483 from $t = 0$ to $t = 60$ (Fig. 6a). The container was insulated on the top and bottom. Hence, the
484 container was heated from the side wall only. Heat transfer inside the container was dominated
485 by conduction; indeed, almost no temperature difference between the top area and the bottom
486 area was observed. The air and product temperatures near the wall were higher than the
487 temperature in the center. Consequently, the relative humidity near the wall decreased
488 (Fig. 7a), promoting product dehydration and slightly higher water vapor content in the air at
489 this location. The air then carried water vapor upward and downward into the colder central
490 area (maximum velocity: $2.8 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ at 60 minutes, Fig. 9). Then, the air came into contact with
491 the cold product which had a temperature lower than the dew point. Consequently, water vapor
492 in the air condensed on the product surface (Fig. 8a), with the highest water condensation
493 occurring at the top area D, (separated from the side wall) as observed experimentally.

494 After the heating phase, the container was placed again in the refrigerator (4°C). The
495 container was cooled from the side wall, resulting in a decrease in the product temperature near
496 the side wall. The product temperature near the wall was lower than the product temperature in
497 the central area at 120 minutes (Fig. 6b). This temperature difference caused air in the warmer
498 area to flow upward and downward into the colder areas (maximum velocity: $0.6 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ at 120
499 minutes, Fig. 9). As this air moved, it transported water vapor from the warmer areas to the
500 colder areas. As can be seen in Fig. 7b, relative humidity at 120 minutes was oversaturated in

501 the container. Water condensate remained in the container in the top area D and a large amount
502 of water condensation was observed near the wall (Fig. 8b).

503 4.2 Air and product temperature and water condensation in the container without 504 insulation

505 In the container without insulation at the top and bottom (Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b), the
506 results show relatively good agreement between the simulated and measured temperatures for
507 both the air and the product. During the first 60 minutes, the container (initially at 4°C) was
508 exposed to 20°C. It was heated by the walls on all sides. The air and product temperatures in
509 the container without insulation exhibited similar behavior to those in the container with
510 insulation at the top and bottom; nevertheless, both the experiments and model predictions
511 showed that the air and product temperatures in the container without insulation increased to a
512 greater extent than those in the container with insulation. At 60 minutes, the highest
513 experimental air temperature was 14.3°C in area D of the container without insulation,
514 compared to 13.6°C in area D of the container with insulation. Similarly, the highest
515 experimental product temperature was 13.2°C in area D of the container without insulation,
516 while it was 12.7°C in area D of the container with insulation.

517 The error between the simulated and experimental results for the air and product
518 temperatures is presented in Table 5. The greatest difference between the simulated and
519 experimental data was 1.4°C for the air temperature in area B and D and 2.1°C for the product
520 temperature in area B.

521 At 60 minutes (at the end of heating), the experimental water condensation on the
522 product surface in the container without insulation was 0.49 g.m⁻³ of product. Whereas the
523 predicted one was lower: 0.30 g.m⁻³ of product (Table 6). As shown in Fig. 11a, area B showed
524 the highest experimental water condensation: 0.17 g.m⁻³ of product. The condensed water on

525 the blueberries' surface is shown in Fig. 11b. Area D showed the highest simulated and
526 experimental water condensation, similar to the condensation pattern observed in the insulated
527 container. However, the condensation became more widely distributed.

528 The simulated water condensation in each area is shown in Fig. 11c. Water condensation
529 in every area increased during the first 60 minutes, when the container was exposed to a warm
530 temperature. After that, the amount of water condensate in areas A and B decreased, while water
531 condensate in areas C and D continued to increase when the container was stored in the
532 refrigerator.

533 The temperature, relative humidity and water condensation distribution in the container
534 without insulation (Supplementary Materials, Section A.4) were similar to those in the container
535 with insulation. However, the water condensation occurred widely across the top areas of the
536 container without insulation. The water condensation highly occurred at the top, separated from
537 the lateral wall.

538 4.3 Effect of variations in parameters

539 Sensitivity analysis was carried out to quantify the relative importance of several
540 parameters in the case of top and bottom insulation exposed to 20° for 60 minutes. The value
541 of permeability, equivalent thermal conductivity, convective heat transfer coefficient, skin mass
542 transfer resistance and effective mass diffusivity were varied individually keeping the reference
543 value for the other parameters. The objective is notably to see if the experimental or numerical
544 discrepancy observed for condensation with reference parameters can be reduced.

545 To study, the effect of the convective heat transfer coefficient and effective mass
546 diffusivity, these parameters were adjusted to their maximum and minimum values, as detailed
547 in Section 2.4. For skin mass transfer resistance, the maximum value ($0.955 \times 10^{-9} \text{ kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}.\text{Pa}^{-1}$)
548 and minimum value ($3.39 \times 10^{-9} \text{ kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}.\text{Pa}^{-1}$) were used based on Becker et al. (1996).

549 Conversely, permeability and equivalent thermal conductivity varied by increasing and
550 decreasing by 20% of their reference values as shown in Table 7.

551 As shown in Fig. 12a, the equivalent thermal conductivity is the primary parameter
552 affecting significantly the evolution of product temperatures. This is attributed to conduction
553 heat transfer as the dominant mechanism. Conversely, effective mass diffusivity plays a crucial
554 role in determining water condensation, as shown in Fig. 12b. Using the highest value of D_{eff}
555 allows a simulation to reach a total condensate mass of 0.46 g.m^{-3} of product, which is close to
556 the experimental value (0.55 g.m^{-3} of product). In Fig. 12c, the simulated amount of water
557 condensation increased in all areas using the highest value of D_{eff} compared to the reference
558 condition. The percentage of condensed water increased in all areas while the percentage of
559 condensed water in area D decreased when using the highest value of D_{eff} was applied.

560 Table 8 shows the variations in temperature and water condensation at 60 minutes for
561 each parameter relative to the reference condition. The equivalent thermal conductivity is the
562 most impactful parameter for air and product temperatures, resulting in a difference of
563 approximately 0.6°C with the reference, while the influence of other parameters on temperature
564 variation is approximately 0.2°C or less. Effective mass diffusivity has the greatest effect on
565 water condensation, with a difference of 0.18 g.m^{-3} of product from the reference condition,
566 while the influence of other parameters on water condensation is less than 0.05 g.m^{-3} of product.

567

568 **5. Conclusion**

569 Our study investigated water condensation in a bulk fruit container under a cold chain
570 break. Experiments were performed using two different container configurations: one with
571 insulation on the top and bottom, and one without insulation. A heat and mass transfer model

572 for a porous medium under natural convection was developed and tested. The results indicate
573 that the model reliably predicted air and product temperatures across all container
574 configurations subjected to a cold chain break. The model predicted the order of magnitude of
575 condensation. With the reference parameter, the model underestimated condensation, but the
576 sensitivity analysis showed that increasing the effective water vapor diffusivity allowed
577 reduction of the discrepancy without affecting air and product temperatures. The numerical
578 results demonstrated that when the fruit container returned to cold conditions, water on some
579 fruit skins evaporated, leading to lower condensation levels in certain zones. Meanwhile, the
580 limited surface area of fruits in the top corners causes increased condensation, which eventually
581 drips to the bottom, potentially accelerating spoilage in that zone. For future studies, equipping
582 the container base with holes can prevent condensate accumulation.

583 The model in this study provides a useful tool for understanding heat and mass transfer
584 mechanisms in fruit packaging under natural convection. It also offers a foundation for future
585 studies involving more realistic packaging designs, including ventilation and temperature-
586 dependent material properties and complex geometry, such as pallets. This model can support
587 further development toward simplified models.

588

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Figure number	Figure Captions
Fig. 1	a. Geometry used for the insulated container, b. Geometry for the non-insulated container, c. Calculation domain
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Fig. 10	Comparison between experimental and simulated air temperatures in the container without insulation on the top and bottom: a. air temperature, b. product temperature
Fig. 11	a. Experimental and simulated percentage and amount of water condensation (g.m^{-3} of product) in each area in the container without insulation, b. The condensed water on the blueberries' surface, c. Simulated water condensation in the non-insulated container
Fig. 12	a. Parameter variation effect in the model: Product temperature in area A, b. Parameter variation effect in the model: Water condensation, c. Experimental and simulated percentage and amount of water condensation (g.m^{-3} of product) in insulated container comparing the reference condition with the condition using the highest effective diffusivity (D_{eff})

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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709 Fig. 4

a.

b.

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716 Fig. 5

C	D
Experiment 20.0% 0.11±0.02	Experiment 33.3% 0.18±0.02
Simulation 17.8% 0.05	Simulation 67.9% 0.19
A	B
Experiment 15.8% 0.09±0.02	Experiment 30.9% 0.17±0.02
Simulation 3.6% 0.01	Simulation 10.7% 0.03

a.

b.

c.

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

717 Fig. 10

a.

b.

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C		D	
Experiment	21.8%	Experiment	21.1%
	0.11±0		0.10±0.02
Simulation	33.3%	Simulation	56.7%
	0.10		0.17
A		B	
Experiment	21.8%	Experiment	34.7%
	0.11±0.01		0.17±0.02
Simulation	0%	Simulation	10.0%
	0		0.03

a.

b.

c.

725 Fig. 12

a.

b.

C	D
Experiment 20.0% 0.11±0.02	Experiment 33.3% 0.18±0.02
A	B
Experiment 15.8% 0.09±0.02	Experiment 30.9% 0.17±0.02

Experimental results

C	D
Ref 17.8% 0.05 $D_{eff} 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ 19.6% 0.09	Ref 67.9% 0.19 $D_{eff} 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ 54.4% 0.25
A	B
Ref 3.6% 0.01 $D_{eff} 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ 6.5% 0.03	Ref 10.7% 0.03 $D_{eff} 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ 19.6% 0.09

Simulated results

c.

Table number	Table Captions
1	Number of elements and computational time for different meshes
2	Comparison of results at 60 minutes (at the end of heating) between different mesh (A: bottom center and B: bottom external) positions as presented in Fig. 3b
3	Error of air temperature and product temperature between simulated results and measured results in the container with insulation
4	Experimental and simulated water condensation in different scenarios in container with insulation
5	Error of air temperature and product temperature between simulated results and measured results in the container without insulation
6	Experimental and simulated water condensation in container without insulation
7	Reference values and model parameter value ranges used for the sensitivity analysis
8	Parameter variation effect in the model, container with insulation

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733 Table 1.

Mesh	Number of elements	Computational time (s)
Normal	1818	4696
Fine	3532	5096
Finer	8580	12305

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735 Table 2.

	$T_{A,a}$ (°C)	$T_{B,a}$ (°C)	$T_{A,p}$ (°C)	$T_{B,p}$ (°C)	C_2 (g)
Difference between Normal and Finer	-0.011	-0.009	-0.001	-0.002	0.002
Difference between Fine and Finer	-0.003	-0.003	0	0	0.002

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737 Table 3.

Temperature scenarios	Error	$T_{air,A}$	$T_{air,B}$	$T_{air,C}$	$T_{air,D}$	$T_{product,A}$	$T_{product,B}$	$T_{product,C}$	$T_{product,D}$
20°C for 60 minutes	ΔT_{max} (°C)	0.8	1.6	1.0	1.5	0.9	2.0	0.6	0.7
	$RMSE$ (°C)	0.25	0.32	0.28	0.26	0.27	0.37	0.27	0.28
25°C for 120 minutes	ΔT_{max} (°C)	1.1	2.0	0.7	2.8	1.0	2.2	0.9	1.2
	$RMSE$ (°C)	0.37	0.46	0.23	0.79	0.32	0.50	0.30	0.36

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741 Table 4.

Conditions		Water condensation (g.m ⁻³ of product)				
		A	B	C	D	Total
20°C, 60	Exp	0.09±0.02	0.17±0.02	0.11±0.02	0.18±0.02	0.55±0
minutes	Sim	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.19	0.28
25°C, 60	Exp	0.05±0.02	0.17±0.04	0.15±0.01	0.25±0.06	0.62±0.08
minutes	Sim	0.01	0.04	0.08	0.27	0.40
25°C, 120	Exp	0.13±0.02	0.11±0.02	0.45±0.01	0.25±0.05	0.94±0
minutes	Sim	0.02	0.05	0.21	0.43	0.71

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743 Table 5.

	T _{air,A}	T _{air,B}	T _{air,C}	T _{air,D}	T _{product,A}	T _{product,B}	T _{product,C}	T _{product,D}
ΔT_{max}	0.9	1.4	0.5	1.4	1.0	2.1	0.9	0.9
(°C)								
<i>RMSE</i>	0.19	0.31	0.25	0.31	0.23	0.40	0.35	0.40
(°C)								

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745 Table 6.

Scenario		Water condensation (g.m ⁻³ of product)				
		A	B	C	D	Total
20°C, 60	Exp	0.11±0.01	0.17±0.02	0.11±0	0.10±0.02	0.49±0.04
minutes	Sim	0	0.03	0.10	0.17	0.30

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747 Table 7.

Parameters	Reference	Range
Convective heat transfer coefficient h , $\text{W.m}^{-2}.\text{K}^{-1}$	5.5	3.4 – 7.6
Skin mass resistance k_s , $\text{kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}.\text{Pa}^{-1}$	2.19×10^{-9}	$0.955 \times 10^{-9} - 3.39 \times 10^{-9}$
Effective mass diffusivity D_{eff} , $\text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-1}$	8.4×10^{-6}	$5.3 \times 10^{-6} - 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$
Permeability K , m^2	2.16×10^{-7}	$\pm 20\%$
Equivalent thermal conductivity k_{eq} , $\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$	0.18	$\pm 20\%$

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749 Table 8.

Parameters	$T_{A,p} - T_{A,p,ref}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$m_{cond} - m_{cond,ref}$ (g.m^{-3} of product)
$h = 3.4$	0.0	-0.02
$h = 7.6$	0.0	0.02
$k_s = 0.955 \times 10^{-9}$	0.1	0.01
$k_s = 3.39 \times 10^{-9}$	0.2	0.05
$D_{eff} = 5.3 \times 10^{-6}$	0.0	-0.06
$D_{eff} = 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$	0.0	0.18
$K = 1.73 \times 10^{-7}$	0.0	0.02
$K = 2.59 \times 10^{-7}$	0.0	0.02
$k_{eq} = 0.14$	-0.6	0.02
$k_{eq} = 0.22$	0.6	-0.02

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